

OPTIMIZATION OF ENDOSCOPIC TREATMENT METHODS IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE PANCREATITIS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15104757>

Relevance: Acute pancreatitis (AP) is a serious pathology of the abdominal organs, which to this day is one of the most important problems of emergency abdominal surgery. Indeed, the incidence and consistently high mortality rates are confirmed by the indicators. The etiological factors of pancreatitis are mainly gallstone disease, alimentary tract, and alcoholism. Acute pancreatitis of biliary etiology occurs in about 30-50% of cases in European and North American countries, while the overall mortality rate is about 10% and has almost no tendency to decrease. With destructive pancreatitis, pancreatic necrosis, it reaches 75%.

Objective: To optimize the use of retrograde endoscopic techniques to reduce complications, mortality, and improve outcomes in patients with acute pancreatitis.

Material and methods. All patients with acute pancreatitis treated in the surgical department of the 3rd clinic of the ADTI and the surgical departments of the ASMSH from 2020 to 2024 participated in the study. All patients were admitted to the emergency department as an emergency or transferred from specialized departments with clinical manifestations of acute pancreatitis. The majority of the study included patients aged 21 to 65 years. 100 men (43 percent), 100 women (57 percent). The average age of the patients was 44 +/- 2.0 years. The patients were mainly divided into 2 groups. 36 patients in group 1 were treated retrospectively with standard conservative drugs. Group 2 included 32 patients who underwent endoscopic papillosphincterotomy and stenting of the Wirsung tract in combination with the Santdart conservative method.

Results and discussion.

The results of treatment of patients with pancreatitis and pancreatic necrosis complicated by endoscopic methods of pancreatic duct decompression depend on the nature of pancreatic necrosis and the time of onset of the disease. In group I, patients were hospitalized in the late stages with various complications after laparotomy, external drainage of the common bile duct, and 28% (10) of patients died, while in group II, patients underwent laparotomy, endoscopic papillosphincterotomy and stenting of the Wirsung tract with the

Santdart conservative method. Thus, based on the obtained data, in order to accurately diagnose pancreatic necrosis, we recommend that abdominal ultrasound and CT be performed in the first hours (initial 2-6 hours) of the patient's hospitalization.

Conclusion: Thus, endoscopic operations in patients with pancreatic necrosis are performed as part of a complex of therapeutic interventions in patients with pancreatic necrosis. They are performed early in the course of pancreatic necrosis. The volume of endoscopic interventions depends on the etiology of the disease, the state of the bile ducts and the pancreatic ducts (Wirsung). In addition, the availability of trained doctors and specialized hospital departments with experience in the treatment of patients with pancreatic necrosis and endoscopic interventions in the bile ducts and pancreatic ducts is of great importance in reducing the number of complications of pancreatic necrosis and death, and endoscopic operations should be performed by a qualified endoscopist.

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